

Evaluation of crystalline state properties of alkali hydrides and deuterides

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Manuscript received 22 March 2007, revised 5 June 2007, accepted 11 June 2007

Abstract : The cohesive energy, atomization energy, Grünelsen parameter, Anderson-Grünelsen parameter, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter, force constant, compressibility, absorption IR frequency and Debye temperature of alkali hydrides and deuterides have been computed using the three standard short-range potential forms due to Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Varshini-Shukla. The calculated values have been compared with the experimental values available in the literature. They are fairly in agreement with the experimental values. It is observed that the force constant, IR absorption frequency and Debye temperature of alkali hydrides and deuterides have almost similar results when computed for the three models. They show variation only in the third and fourth places after the decimal which may not be experimentally significant.

Keywords : Alkali hydrides, alkali deuterides, crystalline state.

The nature of binding in ionic crystals plays a very important role in the solid state physics. Various attempts have been made to understand the nature of binding between the atoms of an ionic crystal and hence to decide the form of interaction potential for such a crystal. Once the reliable form of interaction potential is known it is possible to study the crystalline state properties of ionic crystals. The crystal state properties of alkali hydrides and deuterides have been studied by several investigators. These workers employed the interaction potential models¹⁻³ but none of them is capable enough of explaining all the observed macroscopic properties of ionic crystals. The search for the potential function satisfying the essential requirement of ideal potential continues. In the present study, we have applied Born-Mayer⁴, Hellmann⁵ and Varshini-Shukla⁶ short-range repulsive potential to evaluate the crystalline state properties of alkali hydrides and deuterides. The reason for selecting these models is their suitability in evaluating the crystalline state as well as the molecular state properties of diatomic ionic crystals. Moreover, these potentials fulfill the fundamental physical requirements of an ideal potential.

Cohesive energy :

The lattice-energy per ion-pair of a diatomic crystal can be written as

$$W(r) = W_e + W_{SR} + W_v \quad (1)$$

Here, W_e is the long-range electrostatic Coulomb energy with Madelung constant A . It is usually given by

$$W_e = -Az^2e^2/r \quad (2)$$

where ze is the electronic charge on the ions and r is the equilibrium interionic distance.

The second term, W_{SR} , on R.H.S. of eq. (1) is the short-range repulsive potential dominant in the diatomic crystals. It is related to the overlap integrals through the concept of exchange charge interactions. The potential parameters S_i , ρ and b appearing in W_{SR} have been calculated by using the crystal stability and compressibility conditions⁷.

Table 1. Values of cohesive energy (W ; kJ mol⁻¹) and atomization energy (E_a ; kJ mol⁻¹) for alkali hydrides and deuterides

Crystal	W				E_a			
	BM	HM	VS	Expt. values ¹⁷	BM	HM	VS	Expt. values ¹⁸
LiH	951.05	939.71	926.28	908.04	505.53	494.19	480.76	469.8
LiD	965.16	956.14	945.46	-	515.45	506.43	495.75	-
NaH	826.32	820.11	813.06	795.90	405.00	398.79	391.74	384.1
NaD	844.55	840.79	836.62	-	419.04	415.28	411.11	-
KH	724.87	720.70	716.09	701.82	380.65	376.48	371.87	368.2
KD	759.64	758.52	757.34	-	411.23	410.11	408.93	-
RbH	692.59	689.11	685.30	674.52	364.17	360.69	356.88	384.9
CsH	666.20	663.18	659.90	645.54	365.18	362.16	358.88	343.1

The third term on R.H.S. of the eq. (1) represents the van der Waals energy expressed as

$$W_v = -C/r^6 - D/r^8 \quad (3)$$

where C and D are the dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients. Values of C and D have been calculated, using

and interpolation scheme based on the Slater-Kirkwood variational method^{8,9}.

Atomization energy :

The atomization energy of the ionic crystals gives much better idea of the stability of the crystals than the cohesive energy. The atomization energy of the ionic crystal may also be calculated from the interaction potential function using the simple relation,

$$E_u = W(r) + E - I \quad (4)$$

where E is the electron affinity and I is the ionization energy. In the present calculation the values of E and I have been taken from literature^{10,11}.

Table 2. Values of force constant (f ; 10^4 Nm^{-1}), compressibility (β ; barye^{-1}), IR absorption frequency (ν_o ; 10^{12} Hz) and Debye temperature (θ_D ; K) for alkali hydrides and deuterides

Crystal	f		β		ν_o		θ_D		
	BM	Ref. ¹⁹	BM	Ref. ¹⁹	BM	Ref. ¹⁹	BM	Ref. ¹⁹	Expt. values ¹⁹
LiH	4.21	4.26	2.91	2.90	26.91	27.08	1292.25	1300.03	920
LiD	5.15	4.26	2.36	2.87	22.48	20.32	1079.39	975.5	-
NaH	3.35	4.22	4.37	3.47	22.93	25.77	1101.09	1237.3	-
NaD	4.22	4.22	3.46	3.46	18.58	892.05	892.1	-	-
KH	2.53	4.19	4.11	4.09	19.77	25.43	949.06	1221.0	-
KD	4.18	4.19	4.07	4.08	18.20	18.21	873.66	874.3	-
RbH	3.35	4.18	7.71	4.34	18.89	25.21	906.87	1210.4	-
CsH	2.22	1.17	9.05	4.59	13.03	25.12	625.47	1206.3	-

The calculated values of cohesive and atomization energies of alkali hydrides and deuterides have been listed in Table 1 along with their experimental values. The close agreement between the two highlights the validity of the potential models taken into consideration.

Table 3. Values of Grüneisen parameter (γ ; dimensionless), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ ; dimensionless), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1 ; dimensionless) for alkali hydrides and deuterides

Crystal	C_1				γ				δ_s			
	BM	HM	VS	Expt. values ²⁰	BM	HM	VS	Expt. values ²⁰	BM	HM	VS	Expt. values ²⁰
LiH	2.54	2.75	2.95	2.77	0.77	0.87	0.98	1.21	1.54	1.75	1.95	2.16
LiD	3.20	3.34	3.48	-	1.10	1.17	1.24	-	2.20	2.34	2.48	2.15
NaH	3.12	3.27	3.42	2.23	1.06	1.34	1.21	1.41	2.12	2.27	2.42	2.80
NaD	3.70	3.79	3.88	-	1.35	1.40	1.44	-	2.70	2.79	2.88	2.79
KH	3.42	3.55	3.68	3.42	1.21	1.28	1.34	1.50	2.42	2.56	2.68	3.71
KD	4.64	4.70	4.75	-	1.82	1.85	1.88	-	3.64	3.70	3.75	3.70
RbH	3.60	3.72	3.84	3.49	1.30	1.36	1.42	1.57	2.60	2.72	2.84	4.15
CsH	3.77	3.89	4.00	3.46	1.39	1.44	1.50	1.61	2.72	2.89	3.00	4.65

Force constant (f), compressibility (β), IR absorption frequency (ν_o) and Debye temperature (θ_D) : The force constant f is defined as¹²

$$F = 1/3 [\Phi''(r_o) + 2 r_o^{-1} \Phi'(r_o)] \quad (5)$$

where $\Phi(r)$ is the non-Coulombic part of $W(r)$.

The compressibility β is related to the force constant as

$$\beta = 3k_1 r_o f \quad (6)$$

where r_o is the equilibrium interionic distance in crystalline states. Its values are taken from Sinha *et al.*¹³.

The IR absorption frequency (ν_o) is given by

$$\nu_o = 1/2\pi^{(f/m)^{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

where m is the reduced mass.

Once the value of ν_o is obtained, the Debye temperature θ_D can be calculated from the relation,

$$\theta_D = h \nu_o / k \quad (8)$$

where h is the Planck's constant and k is the Boltzmann constant.

The calculated values of force constant, compressibility, IR absorption frequency and Debye temperature have been shown in Table 2 along with experimental values. The deviation between the two is negligible.

Grüneisen parameter (γ), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ) and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) :

Grüneisen parameter (γ) can be expressed as

$$\gamma = -r_o/6 W'''(r_o)/W''(r_o) \quad (9)$$

where $W''(r)$ and $W'''(r)$ after to the second and third derivatives of $W(r)$.

Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ) have been calculated

using Chang's relation¹⁴ connecting γ and δ derived on the basis of Dugdele and MacDonald relationship between Grüneisen parameter and change of compressibility with volume¹⁴.

Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 has been calculated for the potential models using the relation¹⁶,

$$C_1 = 1 - \beta W'''(r_0)/27k_1 \quad (10)$$

where β is the compressibility and k_1 is the crystal structure having the values 2 and 1.54 for NaCl and CsCl structures respectively.

The calculated values of Grüneisen parameter and Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter of alkali hydrides and deuterides have been listed in Table 3 along with the experimental values and available literature data.

Results and discussion

A careful examination of Table 1 listing the calculated and the experimental values of cohesive and atomization energies of alkali hydrides and deuterides calculated for Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Varshini-Shukla suggests that there is close agreement between the computed and the observed values. This may establish the validity of the potential models taken into consideration. It can also be said that Varshini-Shukla form of short-range repulsive potential has an edge over the two models as it gives the values of cohesive and atomization energies much nearer to the observed values. The computed values of cohesive and of atomization energies decrease from LiH to CsH.

From the study of Table 2 it can be fairly said that the present computed values of f , β , v_0 and θ_D are in better agreement with the available literature data than the previous calculated values. Sufficient data on deuterides are not available. On a comparison of the computed values of the various parameters for deuterides we observe that the agreement is very close. For RbH and CsH, the values of the various parameters obtained are slightly higher. The experimental values of f , β , v_0 and θ_D are not available in the literature.

It is observed (Table 3) that the average values of C_1 for the Born-Mayer (BM), Hellmann (HM) and Varshini-Shukla (VS) model are respectively 3.50, 3.63 and 375. γ for the VS model is very close to the experimental values²⁰. The previous literature data²¹⁻²³ though not very accurate ones are also pointing in favour of our findings. Similar is the case for δ .

Conclusion :

The present work is an attempt to show the validity of the three interaction models and our method of calculation for the production of various crystalline state properties of alkali hydrides and deuterides.

Acknowledgement

The authors express sincere gratitude to Prof. Md. M. Hasan for his valuable suggestions. We duly recognize the encouragement and help given by Mrs. Nandani during the completion this work. We are extremely thankful to honourable referee for his useful suggestions.

References

1. R. Rydberg, *Z. Phys.*, 1931, **73**, 376.
2. R. Narayan and S. Ramaseshan, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1976, **37**, 395.
3. J. Shankar and M. Kumar, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)*, 1987, **142**, 325.
4. M. Born and J. E. Mayer, *Z. Phys.*, 1932, **A75**, 1.
5. H. Hellmann, *Acta Physica Chemical (USSR)*, 1934, 1913.
6. Y. P. Varshini and R. C. Shukla, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1963, **35**, 130.
7. J. Mandal and B. Ghatak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 145.
8. J. Shankar and J. C. Jain, *Phys. Status Solidi b (Germany)*, 1979, **52**, 675.
9. J. C. Slater and J. G. Kirwood, *Phys. Rev.*, 1931, **37**, 682.
10. M. F. C. Ladd and W. H., *Prog. Solid State Chem.*, 1965, **2**, 378.
11. A. G. Massey, "The Typical Elements", Penguin, Middlesex, 1972.
12. K. S. Krishnan and S. K. Roy, *Proc. R. Soc. A, London (RB)*, 1951, **207**, 447.
13. A. K. Sinha and L. Thakur, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1977, **15**, 115.
14. Y. A. Chang, *Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1967, **28**, 697.
15. J. S. Dugdele and D. K. C. McDonald, *Phys. Rev.*, 1953, **89**, 832.
16. J. R. Bowman, *J. Phys. Chem. (USA)*, 1971, **75**, 1251.
17. T. C. Waddington, "Advances in Inorganic and Radio Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1999, Vol. 1, 157.
18. R. T. Sanderson, "Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1967.
19. A. Rahman and M. M. Hasan, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1988, **26**, 400.
20. G. M. S. Srivastava, G. G. Agarwal and J. Shanker, *Phys. Status Solidi (Germany)*, 1986, **135**, 529.
21. M. S. Ali and M. M. Hasan, *Physica B (Netherland)*, 1991, **168**, 121.
22. S. K. Sipani and V. P. Gupta, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1991, **43**.
23. J. Mandal and B. Ghatak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.